

Tradition, Social Media and Community:

Viewing the Virtual from a Folkloric Perspective

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Introduction

Shewly, a resident of New York City, went viral in 2023, on social media platforms. A remark that she made about Assamese bullies resulted in a flurry of content trolling her, speeding the process of going viral. Although the bullying seemed derogatory and contrary to Facebook's community standards, the attention earned her a vast fan base. Shewly's Facebook activities, including vlogging about daily activities and joking, as allowed by freedom of speech, were constantly scrutinized by followers. Roasting the posts, Shewly was called a "nānī," meaning Grandma, because of age, and the postings reflected a spectrum of interactions, ranging from jesting and criticism to admiration. These activities triggered responses both from a religious element, and from liberals, who regard these activities as degradation, lacking in taste or etiquette.

Shewly emerges as a compelling example, within a cohort of women in New York, who congregate and share experiences within their community, extending their interactions to a broader virtual community. The term "nānī," used to address Shewly, symbolizes familial ties, which is reminiscent of the warm rapport between grandparents and grandchildren and is characterized by affection, humor, storytelling, and teasing—a dynamic traditionally permissible within familial relationships, but less so within male–female interactions, except with brothers-in-law and sisters-in-law, and also, among grandparents and grandchildren in social contexts, in contrast with

liberal settings that emphasize personal autonomy.

Traditionally, the relationship between grandparents and grandchildren in Bangladesh and its diaspora enjoyed relative openness and freedom from censorship of male–female relationships. Criticisms directed at virtual activities, mainly by trolling, highlight anxieties surrounding the expansion of social ties into the virtual realm. Shewly's case exemplifies perceptions of decline, in which older adults engaging in virtual activities risk societal stigma and alienation, with their pursuits dismissed as inappropriate or trivial, despite once being a common part of conventional societies as entertaining individuals extending humorous relations beyond kinship. This dichotomy reflects tensions between intellectual pursuits and leisure activities of the literate population, as inspired by the Enlightenment (see Kant 1983), with preferences often aligned with liberal or religious frameworks.

The debate belongs to the larger view held by religious and liberal members of the Bangladeshi diaspora residing in New York and elsewhere. They regularly express concerns about the contemporary virtual landscape, citing perceived declines in taste, values, norms, and ethics, in regard to the rise of gross online activities. This sentiment echoes remarks made by Mamunur Rashid, a veteran actor and playwright from Bangladesh (Prothom Alo 2023), who regarded contemporary times as declining in taste, in creating viral content.

The dominant standards of decency and the idealized persona characterized by wisdom and "taste" appeared to reflect a shifting cultural paradigm historically dominant among the literate people, which arose following the colonial formation of nations (see Thapar 1960; Sarkar 1979; Bhattacharjee 1986; Rahman 2017), with others taking the revivalist pathway (Jaffrelot 2007), following the surge in virtual activities. This surge was identified as a mass lack of taste, and it was identified with the surge in popular political culture. With time, due to electoral politics, nation-building became a more prominent political and cultural marker of the broader population. People are labeled as liberal, moderate, or radical devils to otherize and win the majority's support.

Amid the concerns, questions persist regarding whether political concepts of a "golden" cherished past, or denial of that past—and view of the present as a time of darkness, ignorance, and lacking in reason, should be the basis for evaluating the virtual era. These questions are particularly significant, given that such judgments may stem from political marketing by political entities, and prompts consideration of how industries—like political parties, the state, and media—construct notions of tradition, heritage, values, ethics, and beliefs. They create contemporary educational and cultural institutes that prepare and train people according to their standards.

This article presents reflections on the root question: why do the religious and liberal Bangladeshi diaspora view the virtual

communities, formed by ordinary people vlogging their day-to-day activities, as trivial and inappropriate, according to taste or religion? Can we contextualize tradition beyond conventional cultural, political, and philosophical frameworks to explore how individuals navigate their realities amid the standards of modernity, rationalism, and secularism, and how their divergent understandings of the world can then be viewed as lacking taste? At the center are the elites citing a “mass lack of taste” of the people within contemporary culture, underscoring tensions between classic and popular paradigms, challenging established norms and worldviews. Therefore, won’t utilizing tradition as a lens for understanding cultural phenomena, as is done by the literate, scholarly, and creative only add to the divide, in view of their widely accepted tastes and standards?

Cultural Changes and Corporeality: Politics and Dislocation as Markers of Tradition

Intertwined with material and cultural changes, tradition forms a complex tapestry that shapes societies’ values, practices, and identities in various trajectories. As Simon J. Bronner (2016) underscored, tradition lies at the heart of folkloric studies, continuing alongside material and cultural shifts. Far from being static, tradition is a practical guide rooted in collective and individual experiences. A contrary force is the manipulation of tradition for political and economic end goals. As a result, “the impact of the media... has tended to standardization of food, dress, language, etc.” (Dundes 1978, 6), which seriously affects people who shape themselves by following those activities. However, with the virtual uprising, the mediation of the media by specialists, like artists, authors, poets, and scholars, has become only one aspect of it, while the public interacts individually with and streams to their communities and even to broader audiences. The Internet has shifted reality away from a media that created a largely one-way communication with people, who

then would worship the literate and sophisticated personas as icons.

Therefore, a critical inquiry into the context of national identity following the literate standardized tradition is imperative. The formative period of nation-building created a trend among people “...who felt nostalgia for the past and/or the necessity of documenting the national consciousness or identity” (Dundes 1978, 1), resulting in the development of the study of folklore. The reason behind this kind of surge was “underlying emotional bonds and feelings of attachment, and their evocation through nationalist language and symbols” (Hearn 2006, 20). Their thoughts include “dominant themes of common descent, territorial belonging and shared language in discourses of national identity” (Hearn 2006, 20). Yet, “nation-builders ... repeatedly exploit” (Hearn 2006, 28) how people view themselves for their end goals through “the influential concept of ‘the invention of tradition,’ which is done by politicians for ‘synthesizing and fabricating a national culture to encourage national loyalties’” (Hearn 2006, 70–71). The creation of a national culture manipulates peoples’ perceptions, ideologies, and thoughts through educational training and by creating an ideal persona that people can dream of becoming—an ideal citizen modeled after primarily media icons, such as writers, philosophers, scientists, and artists—and broadly becoming a part of either ethnic, territorial, internationalist, or religious groups in which they would identify with this ideal persona. (For a reflection on how this cultural manipulation impacted Bangladesh in the late 2000s, see Raju 2023).

The last century witnessed several paradigm shifts that transformed folkloristics significantly, including examining folklore studies. Briggs (2008) advocated interdisciplinary collaboration, challenging traditional boundary-making approaches to foster innovation. In this purview, the criticism of defining “folk” as a homogenous group (Dundes 1978) and defining folklore as artistic communication (Ben-Amos 1971), or as a dynamic group created by performance

(Bauman 1971; see, also, Kapchan 2003), are the making of the questions about nationalism, homogeneity, and diversity that have focused on defining people, instead of viewing them as they are. As a result, folklore could not transcend the question of identity, and therefore, folklorists stress freeing the field from negative history marked by nationalism and homogeneity (see Noyes 2016), thereby remaining bound by philosophical parlance that introduced the necessity of recognizing diversity—another form of underscoring identity.

On the other hand, folklore uniquely combines practice as repeated everyday activities (Bronner 2012) and explores how the practice becomes a worldview—and thus, a philosophical prospect, leaving ideological and political inclination to modernity, rationalism, and secularism, the key components of the “industries”—political parties, state, and media—out of the equation.

Folklore refocuses on ideas and perceptions of tradition and heritage, which encompass the continuity of practices, cultural norms, and beliefs, often imbued with a sense of national identity and statehood. However, the understanding of tradition and its manifestations in folklore genres have changed over time (Bascom 1965, 7–8). Shifts in societal preferences and worldviews occur, particularly, under the influence of advancements in science and technology, accelerating the pace of change by facilitating the widespread dissemination of cultural artifacts (Bronner 2016, 7). This phenomenon is exemplified by the proliferation of viral content, encompassing popular songs, catchphrases, memes, videos, ceremonies, and rituals, which can rapidly reach millions of individuals, thereby attaining viral status, marking a shift from literacy to virtual reality, in which written text or oral communication are no longer defining factors (see Ong 2002).

The virality of cultural content is emblematic of contemporary (virtual) culture, characterized by its dynamic and expansive nature. What Roger Abrahams noted about cultural content (quoted in Bronner [2016,

7) may also apply to viral phenomena, as it also adheres to the general principles governing cultural changes, influenced by the interplay between innovation and stability, as well as the interactions among diverse social groups. Crucially, the dissemination of viral content hinges on individual engagement, whereby individuals either propagate or abstain from sharing such content online. This transmission occurs through oral tradition and technological mediation (Bronner 2016, 9).

Typical forms of viral content take cultural forms, such as rumors, narrative accounts, folk performances, pranks, memes, slogans, slangs, flash mobs, graffiti, and parodies, many of which resonate with themes of contemporary humor, crisis, heritage, tradition, mass mobilization, or simply performances that do or do not adhere to performative standards, and hence, may stand out as simply entertaining (funny, gross, saddening, enraging, or neutral). Such content often undergoes iterative refinement through successive iterations of public events, demonstrations, or mundane activities, disseminating them across virtual platforms and exemplifying the dynamic nature of tradition in the virtual era.

The mutability of tradition is also underscored by shifts in architectural practices, exemplified by transition from old clay, wood, thatch, and bamboo structures to contemporary building materials. The transformation reflects broader socioeconomic shifts, including the transition from agrarian to capitalist economies, and underscores the adaptive nature of tradition and cultural practices in responding to changing material reality. While tradition during the golden era of literacy relied on cultural industries, thus enabling cultural elites, the advent of virtual communication technologies has expanded its reach and transmission mode (Bronner 2016, 14). It has resulted in the dominance of rational view, a resultant output of rationalism—as opposed to the magical, miraculous, and folkloric—becoming a dormant form. Even now, rationalism focuses on demonizing other rationalisms as hoaxes, rumors, and misinformation,

collectively defined as populism. Contemporary viral culture shares similarities with traditional folklore transmission, involving the purposeful dissemination of multilayered messages through social interaction. Despite differences in form and medium, contemporary viral culture inherits the essence of magical, miraculous, and folkloric, as evidenced by the persistence of folkloric elements in technologically mediated content creation (Bronner 2016, 17). Therefore, tradition in this alternative reality is not static but continually adapting and changing, shaped by the dynamic interplay between practices and present material and immaterial circumstances.

The transformation of tradition is intertwined with broader societal changes, including shifts in communication mediums, economic structures, and cultural norms. For many among the Bangladeshi diaspora, for instance, changes in agricultural practices and the advent of digital technologies have reshaped patterns of social interaction and leisure activities. However, the perception of tradition as a nationalist symbol and economic showpiece belies its adaptive nature, wherein tradition adapts in tandem with societal transformations. Consequently, contemporary practices are inherently traditional, embodying ongoing shifts in the dominance of rational cultural norms, values, and corporeality influenced by virtual literacy, in contrast with print and electronic media-dominated literacy that, for years, tried to eradicate the magical, miraculous, and folkloric (Nigam 2020).

Universalization of Western modernity as a “process” (Habermas 1998, 2) and rationalism, alongside a surge in literacy, influenced how populations outside their societal territories can connect under the idea of nationhood and statehood, thus creating a fertile ground for the politicization and commodification of tradition in a selective way (see Anderson 2006). Tradition was dislocated from the folk, who practically live the tradition in their daily lives, by criticizing them as tasteless and tagging them as “popular.” Thus, by connecting them with the hegemonic concept of “populism,” they

were disqualified as being able to reason as defined by Rationalism.

Tradition and Discontinuation: Rationalized Religious and Liberal Spectrum

Motivated by the mass migration of people from Bangladeshi rural households, and thereby, from the magical, miraculous, and folkloric to urban spaces—and, in this case, to the United States economically, politically, and infrastructurally, and to Rationalism—there has been a considerable change in the reality and perception of self by Bangladeshi emigrants.

I often heard that these people become more devout Muslims, as many of my acquaintances from Bangladesh stress that immigrant families adhere more strongly to religious values, which provides them with a common identity in a different culture. Some even consider their financial struggles and illiteracy as the rationale behind their reliance on the miraculous (Dein, Alexander, and Napier 2008).

I have found, however, in visiting different mosques across New York, that rather than having the same tradition of Islam, there are differences in how the Muslims pray, wear clothes, and communicate. And, the belief in the miraculous is not the result of misfortune or illiteracy. Rather, it is part of the Bangladeshi diasporic reality and their practice. And, for those who were born and grew up in Bangladesh, religion stands out as only one component of their identity. They all perceive themselves as Bangladeshis, and even with differences in their locality of origin in Bangladesh, their foodways, clothing, groceries, and even their stores tend to resemble each other. They still have their local cuisines, and from that core, comes their practice and reality. They form regional associations that, at times, can lead to internal conflict in terms of leadership and identity, but are significant to their rites of passage as a diaspora, including but not limited to assisting with childbirth and furthering their education, as well as receiving and helping new

immigrants from Bangladesh, including buying them new clothes and finding them work, and finally, purchasing graves for the deceased. All of these activities meet their needs and values, and in turn, these everyday activities and needs define their traditions.

We need to rethink tradition from this understanding: how can we perceive it? The so-called “ordinary Bangladeshis” among the diaspora in New York City devise practices aligning with their traditions to navigate their way through their new environment. For the liberals, do they take the same pathway? As Dorothy Noyes (2016) explained, they develop impersonal respect determined by affordability. One of the factors in Noyes’ view is that the standard of social status changes with dislocation and becomes more impersonal, and thus, affordability determines their status rather than any ascribed identity, religion, and/or social status stemming from what the industries promote. This seems to be the case among the liberal Bangladeshi diaspora in New York, but they do not constitute the whole diaspora, as there tends to be at least four groups, based on social status, living in the United States:

1. *Literate immigrants and students* who came to the United States through individual effort and feel proud of themselves.

2. *Ayyles* who crossed the border and are thus labeled *Tarjan*, referring to their arduous travel through jungles/borders to make it to the United States. They are usually illiterate or less educated.

3. *Dependent immigrants* brought in by their spouses, who are thus labeled “Petticoat or Lungi” visa holders.

4. *Benefit receivers* who are typically the impoverished portion of the diaspora and do not hold good jobs or own business enterprises. The non-benefit receivers blame this group for misusing their tax money and ridicule them.

Each group tends to undermine the other, and hence, there tend to be trolls, jokes, and fights that ridicule the other groups, but inherently, this activity is centered on the formation of the collective “us” by creating

the “other.” There is an interesting dynamic within the formation of *Nōyākā’ilyā* (people from Noakhali, Bangladesh) and *Silēti* (people from Sylhet, Bangladesh) communities, with negative or humorous intonations due to their high numbers in New York.

Also, the social media troll culture tends to joke about dialects in Bangladesh, aiming for homogenization with the idea of a Bengali nation defined by a Bengali language, among other characteristics. The troll culture around the regional communities, too, is a part of the migrant culture in New York. However, it is not the most important aspect, because it does not wholly describe the relationship dynamics of the diaspora communities, bearing testimony to the changes in the familiar Bangladeshi status ideas, owing to the influence that liberalism has on them.

The question of tradition among the Bangladeshi diaspora pertains to their perception of family, gender roles, and children. Hence, most of them reach a consensus regarding the challenges of changes to family, husband–wife, male–female, and child–parent relationships, as they are exposed to the diverse cultures of New York. There are liberals, consisting primarily of the younger generation, who advocate for change, but the majority of the diaspora population dwell on the insecurity that their family could be destroyed if everyone exercised individualism at the level advocated for by liberalism. What remains most worrisome to them is the insecurity of the enormous changes that have occurred in male–female dynamics, personhood, and legal systems, all of which influence their worldview and idea of family, norms, and values. Their concerns lead some of the diaspora to support conservative politics and prefer Republicans over Democrats.

The traditional social and familial ties are especially practiced and appreciated in Bangladesh among the rural communities. Such societal affairs accommodated the relationship between males and females, where jokes and gestures, often sexual, would have some space beyond conjugal and dryadic

traditions denoting folkloric and cultural traditions that arise specifically within the context of two-person relationships (Oring 2012). Grandparents, brothers-in-law, and sisters-in-law—and not just those from immediate families but also from the neighborhood—would thus be essential liaisons for young, unmarried individuals and newlyweds. The grandparents, brothers-in-law, and sisters-in-law, typically, listen to marriage proposals and love affairs and convey to families the relationship types that they would encourage youths to pursue. In contrast, for other relationships, they would socially frown upon such affairs and even prohibit such communications. Grandparents, brothers-in-law, and sisters-in-law, in particular, would usually play a coach’s role in marriage and other activities of sexuality and reproduction, with friends and peers also allowed such communication.

Modernity and rationalism, advocated by education, played a significant role in social displacement, with people segregating themselves from what once was a socially acceptable way of life. These changes redefined shame and how Muslim families viewed women and men and conducted themselves in their households and elsewhere. At the same time, the changes led to a liberal perception that was critical of tradition and religion and a view of people in terms of their freedom, personal space, democracy, and rationalism. Society and religion came to be viewed as obstacles to freedoms and personal spaces. As such, the social perception of grandparents–grandchildren, and sisters-in-law–brothers-in-law relationships gradually became more gender-focused, introducing the idea of religious regulations or liberal values defining what should be prohibited or perceived as personal freedom, especially around the debate about who should decide relationships of couples beyond their blood relations.

Liberals stress consent between adults as a factor in determining who should enjoy sexual and other forms of freedom, while the religious point to religious regulations rather than looking to family or society for approval, as once was the custom.

As such, practices gradually became limited, not often carried out widely beyond blood relationships—thereby, either freeing individuals as they choose liberal values or confining them to religious practices that stress women hiding their bodies and keeping away from males that are not blood-related.

The Muslim Bangladeshis in New York and Bangladesh hold these two opposing extreme ideals, usually navigating between the two. The literate Bangladeshi diaspora view them as hypocrites (neither purely Muslim nor liberal; neither rebellious nor law-abiding) (see Sofa 2002). Secular education and societal upbringing introduce reason, as do secular law and legislation, resulting in dichotomies that create huge conflicts within persons who need to abide by social norms and values that rely highly on the magical, miraculous, and folkloric aspect of reality.

The social, familial, and religious systems are put into crisis by the secular education system that has instilled the ideal image of personhood in the standard of modernity. The description of a “mass lack of taste” is thus applied to people who hold their own logic and rationalism but, unfortunately, are not deemed as logical and rational, leading to the dehumanization of the ordinary Bangladeshis as hypocrites. Likewise, the liberal and the religious populations tend to see the general populace as obstacles to their perceptions of utopia of an ideal Bangladeshi community. Instead of tradition that marks everyday life and practices, they are dominated by education and a new form of reasoning orchestrated by education.

As an example, the once socially accepted behavior of smoking among women became a taboo, while remaining acceptable for males; yet, parents do not want to allow their children to smoke. Also, families do not want to allow children space that would offer them access to (gender and character) choices. The parents put their children under the supervision of tutors during their free time, thereby occupying their time with religious and professional training that would shape them according to whatever the guardians’ deemed ideal. These practices are

new, even in rural communities that dream of coming to the United States and fulfilling their version of the American dream.

Children once had the chance to dwell in a societal sphere of grandparents (at home) and peers (in the playground), who would play a vital role in their cognitive development and socialization. With modernity, consumerism, religiosity, and career focus, children tend to spend more time away from the traditional social sphere, and thus, their worldviews tend to be quite different from their parents. There is a considerable transformation in the upbringing and cognitive development of children, who seek more freedom or dedicate their lives to careers and/or religion due to the changed circumstances. As such, many children question their parents, families, and backgrounds, looking for the freedom of liberalism. Their worldview is dominated by their love for rights and personal space, which they believe can be achieved only through rebellion (by liberal students) and denouncement (by the religious segment) (see Raju 2023). The same happens with first-generation Americans of Muslim ethnicity, for which there have been movements in Canada and the United States, in which immigrant parents participated and claimed some form of authority over their children and what they should learn (Hobson 2023).

Religious families who value their worldviews carry their mistrust toward the liberal generation, regarding it as decayed. Similarly, their religious reasoning tends to discard traditional upbringing as something irreligious and immoral, and thus, there is another segregation of grandparents’ involvement in the upbringing of children, impeding the process of passing on their knowledge, worldviews, and morality. Also, liberal aristocrats discard the virtual and the religious cultures as meaningless, stupid, and devoid of taste, creating a new lower class in the virtual platforms—TikTokers, vloggers, and singers, who do not meet the media standards of arts, poetry, music, and vlogging.

The literate class’s standard, however, is qualitative and performative, while many of

the personas in social media play a humorous role, as once happened in conventional societies. Thus, their mundane, nonsensical, and ridiculous activities tend to draw audiences that are looking for entertainment within society, instead of going to traditional media platforms. Judging those persons and who follows them by using the qualitative and performative standards of the literate world would leave out its humorous, traditional, and practical aspects. The activities seemingly ridiculous, and thus, “below standard” are the tradition of the virtual era. It has become quite a common practice among individuals to draw people to the content they share on their platform and hope to go viral, because that was the case in societies, too, before the introduction of the entertainment industry—an industry, which now seems to have become the sole proprietor of the standard, as well as the secular model of rationalism, dictating how liberalism and religion reason now.

Shewly, too, is frowned upon because she belongs to an elderly generation that does not speak according to the literate standard. They also fall into the group that does not fit the media standard. As to the questions posed at the start of this article, what is regarded as traditional in political and economic terms are practices defined by customs, beliefs, rituals, and traditions devoid of public participation, with an exception of touristic ventures into museums and archives, just like in the entertainment industry, electoral politics (during elections), and state jurisdiction that take the sole authority of determining standards—thus, making the people passive subscribers who purchase, watch, and vote to decide who will dictate their lives. This paradigm marks an end to a tradition practiced in preliterate eras. Due to a significant change in how everyday activities are transmitted in the virtual realm, literacy-dominated institutions tend to frown upon that which puts their sole proprietorship at stake. On the other hand, the masses, once left out and considered only as subscribers to the popular domain—another version of

cultural elitism—have now taken to the virtual platform to disseminate and transmit narratives, thereby, taking a share of what the once-dominant cultural and political industries did to ensure their dominance over the people's activities.

So, why do the religious and liberal Bangladeshi diaspora view the virtual communities formed by the ordinary, through vlogging their day-to-day activities, as trivial and inappropriate, based on their own standards of taste or religion? Because they have created their worldview through discontinuation from the past, created mainly by those industries, the state being the biggest of them, and the practices followed by Shewly tend to offend them and make them look away. Therefore, can we contextualize tradition beyond conventional cultural, political, and philosophical frameworks and explore how individuals navigate their realities amid the standard of modernity, rationalism, and secularism formed by the industries, and which often question people's divergent understandings of the world as lacking taste?

At the center lies the elitism, citing a "mass lack of taste," within contemporary culture, underscoring tensions between classic and popular paradigms, challenging established norms and worldviews defined by their needs and activities. Do they lack "taste"? That, once again, will be a qualitative answer pertaining to the idea of sophisticated taste and should apply to the literate and trained professionals of the industries—but not to the people for whom practice and everyday activities are their markers—and must be judged by how they derive practices, but not like that of a literate consumer or maker who consumes or creates commodities for higher than ordinary life's sake. Therefore, utilizing tradition as a commodity that popularized literate, scholarly, and creative people as producers of content and consumers created a divide in the name of their universal taste and standard and rendered passive the active societal, familial, and everyday aspects of life in Bangladesh and elsewhere. The virtual era is thus a new time and domain, in which passive people become active, and

so, tradition changes from its archival and nationalist confines.

Conclusion: Question of Religious and Modernist Appropriation in Determining the Bangladeshi Standards

Shewly immigrated to America from Sylhet, Bangladesh, bringing the experiences of a traditional rural household and aligning them with a new material and political reality. She was exposed to a new reality in which individuals apparently have abundant space and freedom, a stark contrast to the contemporary transformation in Bangladesh. As an elder, Shewly chose personal freedom over strict religious adherence, which many still practice. The bond established with the audience allows Shewly the freedom to humor the virtual community, creating a new sphere for the grandparent–grandchild relationship, defined by their unique interaction.

Outsiders may struggle to understand their communication, as their shared terms and jargon facilitate rapid, natural interaction within their group (Nadziejka 1992, 663). No matter how small or temporary, every interaction develops common meaningful referents and collective memories (Fine 2018, 8). These cultural elements evolve through group interactions, and the virtual gathering of Shewly's community is crucial for their communication to develop. Shewly's vlogs reflect their social and cultural reality. Unlike the institutional boundaries that often dismiss popular culture as meaningless, Shewly comes from a generation that socially defined life. In New York, they experience a different cultural environment where freedom of speech and expression is somewhat upheld. However, this understanding may not be shared by everyone in the diverse audience whom the videos reach, viewing the contents with varied worldviews, making the context sometimes challenging to grasp.

When Shewly commented on Assamese bullies, it drew criticism from that community, which felt hurt by the remark, leading

to an apology. Similarly, some people from Bangladesh criticized Shewly for relying solely on the idea of freedom. Despite the criticism, she continues her activities, unbowed by religious and nationalist pressures. However, as a transmitted narrative, the videos become refined and edited, giving meanings based on the idea of taste(s) shaped by state and cultural industries, and often undermining the reality of the mass public and their everyday practices. Important questions about tradition, culture, and practice are raised, which are often perceived as something archived through the lens of the literate standard, motivated by politics and commodification. It is crucial to understand these concepts, not as rigid political constructs or commodified forms, but as practical instruments that people use daily. Tradition should be seen as a guide that shapes how people perceive the world, based on their experiences, applying old lessons to new situations.

The literate tradition has created a labyrinth of statehood, nationalism, and standardized culture, promoting utopian ideals of equality, freedom, and equity (Habermas 1998, 15). However, it often labels everyday people's beliefs and practices as obstacles, branding them as "irrational," and hence, legendary and mythical (Asad 2003, 13–14). This charge induces a sense of guilt and compels conformity to intellectual standards set by state-run industries, denying individuals any alternative reality.

The rise of virtual culture poses a significant challenge to traditional statehood models, which rely on literacy and secular knowledge based on facts to regulate daily life. This shift prompts a reevaluation of democracy, freedom, and equality, as celebrated under the project and process of modernity. We can, therefore, argue that the era that disseminated modernity is that of literacy. Has the virtual era begun to mark a new transition from it?

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About the Guest Editor

Rasel Ahmed is a Bangladeshi folklorist, author, and translator based in New York. His research delves into folklore as a dynamic, lived experience, challenging the theoretical and often idealized perspectives of modernity, rationalism, and Enlightenment. Rasel's work seeks to uncover the cyclical and iterative nature of folklore as a counterpoint to linear narratives of progress. His first book, *Ādhunikatā, Jātīyatābāda o Rājanītira Kalpita Mānuṣēra Binirmāṇa: Cabbiṣēra Abhyut'thānōttara Bānlādēśa Adhyāyanēra Bhatti (Deconstruction of Modernity, Nationalism, and Politics' Imagined Human: Foundation of the Study of Bangladesh Post-2024 Revolution)*, is a Bengali academic text exploring the intersections of cultural memory, modernity, identity, and politics outside the social memory of the people in the wake of Bangladesh's 2024 revolution. The book delves into how these forces historically operated outside the collective social memory of the people in the context of Bangladesh's transformation.